

Arbuscular mycorrhizal association with important medicinal plants of Sagar*

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ABSTRACT: Five medicinal plants viz. *Ocimum sanctum*, *Mentha arvensis*, *Centella asiatica*, *Oxalis corniculata* and *Acorus calamus*, belonging to four different families such as Lamiaceae, Apiaceae, Oxalidaceae and Araceae were studied for their Arbuscular Mycorrhizal (AM) association. All the test plants were growing in the Botanical Garden of Dr. H.S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.). The result revealed that all the five medicinal plants had AM association in the roots and spore population in the rhizospheric soil. However, percent root colonization, spore population and AMF species varied from plant to plant. Maximum percent root colonization and spore population of AM fungi was observed in *Ocimum sanctum* followed by *Centella asiatica*, *Mentha arvensis* and *Oxalis corniculata*, whereas minimum root colonization and spore population was observed in *Acorus calamus*. Total 14 AMF species were identified and quantified in which *Glomus* spp. were found dominate followed by *Acaulospora* spp. and *Sclerocystis* spp. *Gigaspora* spp. were found poorly distributed.

Key words: Arbuscular mycorrhizal association, medicinal plants, rhizosphere, spore population, *Glomus* spp.

Arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi are important components of natural eco-systems and strongly influence the plant community composition and eco-system function (Hart and Klironomos, 2002; Bever *et al.*, 2002). AM fungi are known to be geographically ubiquitous and occur over a broad range of dissimilar environments (Gerdemann and Trappe 1974; Koske, 1987) from the arctic to the tropics and occupy a wide range of ecological niches (Shrivastava *et al.*, 1996). They are commonly associated with plants in agriculture, horticulture pastures and tropical forests. More than 80 percent of all plants form relationship with AM fungi in their root system (Smith and Read, 1997). According to Gupta *et al.* (1994/1995) AM fungi have also been observed in association with medicinal and aromatic plants. Mycorrhizal relationship is complex, subtle and affect above ground community structure in a variety of ways. The colonized host plants derive several benefits from this symbiotic fungal association particularly enhanced plant growth by augmenting the nutrient

uptake (Pierzynski *et al.*, 2000; Sen, 2000) especially the phosphorus (Hayman, 1982; Harley and Smith, 1983) and uptake of other essential elements like N, K, Zn, Mg, Ca and S. (Abbott and Robson 1984). AM also providing increased protection against root pathogens and environmental stresses including drought (Subramanian *et al.*, 1995), cold (Charest *et al.*, 1993), salinity (Davis and Young, 1985) and pollution (Giri *et al.*, 2000). These days many people are cultivating medicinal plants to fulfil the increasing demands of pharmaceutical industries. Thus prompted with the above mentioned facts we undertook present study to understand how native AM fungi play their role in association with test medicinal plants so that their bio-fertilizing potential can be exploited accordingly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Roots and rhizospheric soil samples of five different test medicinal plants were collected from the medicinal garden of Department of Botany, Dr. H.S. Gour University Sagar, situated in the North of Tropic of Cancer between 23°5' -24°25'N and 78°10' -79°15'E on an average altitude of - 517m above mean sea level.

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*This paper is dedicated to late Prof. K.M. Vyas

The test plants were grown by seeds (*Ocimum sanctum*), suckers (*Centella asiatica* and *Mentha arvensis*), bulbs (*Oxalis corniculata*) and rhizome (*Acorus calamus*). The root samples were collected from 16 week old plants and brought to laboratory which were then washed gently in tap water and cut into pieces of 1 cm. in length. Root segments were cleared and stained according to the methods of Phillips and Hayman (1970) and the extent of root colonization was measured according to the method of Giovannetti and Mosse (1980).

Spore isolation was done by wet sieving and decanting method of Gerdemann and Nicolson (1963). Identification of AM fungal spore was done as per the manual of Schenck and Perez (1990).

RESULTS

The data of percent root colonization and spore population are presented in table 1. The result shows that all the test medicinal plants are colonized by AM fungi. However, spore population and percent root colonization varied from plant to plant. Maximum percent root colonization was found in *Ocimum sanctum* (81%) followed by *Centella asiatica* (78%) then *Mentha arvensis* and *Oxalis corniculata* 65% and 62% respectively. Minimum percent root colonization was found in *Acorus calamus* (47%). Both vesicles and arbuscules were found in the root segments of different test plants. Vesicles were almost common in all the test plants but their frequency was higher in *Ocimum sanctum* and *Centella asiatica* whereas arbuscules were observed only in *Mentha arvensis*.

Maximum number of spores were found in the rhizospheric soil of *Ocimum sanctum* (931/100g of soil) followed by *Centella asiatica* (907/100g of soil), *Mentha arvensis* (836/100g of soil) and *Oxalis corniculata* (819/100g of soil) and minimum spore number was recorded in the rhizospheric soil of *Acorus calamus* (620/100g of soil).

Total numbers of 14 different AM fungal spp. were recorded from the rhizospheric soil of five different test medicinal plants. *Ocimum sanctum* shows maximum (12) AM fungi followed by *Centella asiatica* and *M. arvensis* 10 AM fungi each and *Oxalis corniculata* 8 AMF whereas minimum (6) AM fungi were recorded in *Acorus calamus*.

Among 14 different AM fungal spp. *Glomus* spp. were dominant followed by *Acaulospora* spp. and *Sclerocystis* spp. whereas *Gigaspora* spp. was poorly distributed. Among the different species of the genus *Glomus*, *Gl. aggregatum* dominates and found with all the five test medicinal plants followed *Gl. fasciculatum*, which also found with all the plants except *Oxalis corniculata*.

DISCUSSION

The root colonization by AM fungi is a dynamic process. The percent root colonization and the spore population in the rhizosphere are the result of root exudation (Elmer, 2002; Kape *et al.*, 1992). The quantity and type of AM strains also affect the dynamics of root colonization, which were increased by increasing the age of plant (Chandra and Jamaluddin, 1995).

The result obtained from the present study suggests that all the test plants viz. *Ocimum sanctum*, *Mentha arvensis*, *Centella asiatica*, *Oxalis corniculata*, and *Acorus calamus* show good root colonization. However, percent root colonization as well as number of AM spores and AM fungal species varied from plant to plant. It is clearly evident from the results that members of family Lamiaceae (*Ocimum sanctum* and *Mentha arvensis*) and *Centella asiatica* (Apiaceae) show greater colonization as compared to *Acorus calamus* (Araceae) and *Oxalis corniculata* (Oxalidaceae). The variability in the spore population and AM species in different test medicinal plants may be interpreted on the basis of their respective root exudation (Buee *et al.*, 2000; Tawaraya *et al.*, 1996). The greater number of AM spores and AM fungal species occurred in the rhizosphere of *Ocimum sanctum*, *Centella asiatica* and *Mentha arvensis* probably due to the leeching of more carbon and lesser amount of other secondary toxic substances. The occurrence of lesser number of AM spores and AMF species in the rhizosphere of *Acorus calamus* and *Oxalis corniculata* may be due to the exudation of lesser carbon and greater toxic substances. This investigation is in accord with the findings made by Mohan and Mahadevan (1984) and they reported that secondary toxic substances, which were present in high concentration in the plant roots influenced the association of mycorrhizae with the plant.

Table 1. Distribution of spore population, percent root colonization, total number of AM fungal species and dominant AM species in five different medicinal plants

S. No.	Plant Name	Family	Spore population in 100 gm ⁻¹ rhizospheric soil	Root colonization (%)	Total number of VAM fungal species	Average no. of vesicles in cm ³ root bit	Percent arbuscules in cm ³ root bit	Dominant VAM species
1.	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Araceae	620	47	6	22	-	AGDM, LAGR, LHOI, LFSC, SSNS
2.	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Apiaceae	907	78	10	37	-	AGDM, ADTC, LFSC, LCLR, LAGR, GABD, SPCC, SSNS
3.	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	Lamiaceae	836	65	10	11	87	ASCB, ADTC, LFSC, LAGR, LMSS, LMTC, GRSA, SPCC
4.	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Lamiaceae	931	81	12	42	-	AGDM, ADTC, LAGR, LFSC, LHOI, LHTS, LCLR, GABD, SPCC
5.	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	Oxalidaceae	819	62	8	28	-	ASCB, LMSS, LAGR, LCLR, GABD, SSNS

Species code as per Perez and Schenck (1990)

Abbreviations:

AGDM	: <i>Acaulospora gerdemannii</i>	Schenck & Nicolson	LCLR	: <i>Glomus clarum</i>	Nicolson & Schenck
ASCB	: <i>A. scrobiculata</i>	Trappe	LMTC	: <i>G. multicaule</i>	Gerdemann & Bakshi
ADTC	: <i>A. denticulata</i>	Sieverding & Toro	LHTS	: <i>G. heterosporum</i>	Smith & Schenck
LAGR	: <i>Glomus aggregatum</i>	Schenck & Smith	GABD	: <i>Gigaspora albida</i>	Schenck & Smith
LFSC	: <i>G. fasciculatum</i>	Thaxter	GRSA	: <i>G. rosea</i>	Nicolson & Schenck
LHOI	: <i>G. hoi</i>	Brech & Trappe	SPCC	: <i>Sclerocystis pachycaulis</i>	Wu & Chen
LMSS	: <i>G. mosseae</i>	Gerdemann & Trappe	SSNS	: <i>S. sinuosa</i>	Gerdemann & Bakshi

Table 2. Physico-Chemical properties of the rhizospheric soil samples

Colour	Odour	Physical Properties					Chemical Properties									
		Mechanical Texture		Lab Texture	Condu- ctivity (sm ⁻¹)	pH	Base Defici- ency	N hac.	P hac.	K hac.	Organic C%	Solubl Salts Milli Mohl	CaCO ₃ %	Zn (ppm)	Cu (ppm)	
		Sand %	Silt %													Clay %
Red	Pungent	39.28	23.84	36.88	Clay Loam	0.43	7.4	Medium	455	14.4	213.75	1.80	0.17	2.5	0.32	1.36

Here it is clearly evident from the results that only *Glomus aggregatum* was found associated with all five medicinal plants and *Glomus fasciculatum* except with *Oxalis corniculata*. Other AMF were found to be randomly distributed. However, according to Gupta *et al.* (1994/1995) spore population and root colonization were two different things. Recently Mohan *et al.* (2005), Gupta *et al.* (2004) reported direct correlation between percent root colonization and spore population. It may be presumed that *O. sanctum* and *C. asiatica* show their highly mycotrophic nature. This is in accordance with Gupta *et al.* (2000) and Mohan *et al.* (2005). Other test medicinal plants were less dependent on AM fungi for their survival. Such host differences on the effectivity of AM has been reported earlier by Jakobsen (1994).

Dominance of *Glomus* from this region was earlier reported by us (Dwivedi and Vyas 2002; Vyas and Soni 2004; Vyas *et al.*, 2006). However, Gai and Liu (2003) reported that alkaline pH favours the occurrence of *Glomus* whereas acidic pH favours the *Gigaspora* and *Scutellospora*. Since the pH of soil of botanical garden is slightly alkaline therefore we may corroborated these findings with earlier reports (Dwivedi, 2003).

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